

Glacial landforms and deglaciation chronology of the SE sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia.

Version 1

Description

This project aims to gain new knowledge on palaeo-ice flow dynamics and deglaciation patterns from the glacial landform record of the southeastern sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet during the last deglaciation in Latvia. To achieve this, the glacial inversion method based on glacial landform mapping, palaeo-ice flowset and ice margin retreat pattern reconstructions supported by chronological data will be used.

The descriptions of the data are provided, including the descriptions on the manually mapped glacial landforms (e.g. subglacial bedforms, eskers, crevasse-squeeze ridges and marginal formations), the results of the glacial landform mapping via machine learning, and the collected and newly obtained absolute dates (C-14, Be, OSL etc.) of sediments and landforms related to the deglaciation of the SE sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia with the lines of the ice-margin positions. The data consists of three datasets described separately.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Reconstruction of ice stream dynamics and deglaciation of the SE sector of the

Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia
(Izp-2024/1-0193)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Glacial landforms and deglaciation chronology of the SE sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia.](#)

Description:

This project aims to gain new knowledge on palaeo-ice flow dynamics and deglaciation patterns from the glacial landform record of the southeastern sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet during the last deglaciation in Latvia. To achieve this, the glacial inversion method based on glacial landform mapping, palaeo-ice flowset and ice margin retreat pattern reconstructions supported by chronological data will be used.

The descriptions of the data are provided, including the descriptions on the manually mapped glacial landforms (e.g. subglacial bedforms, eskers, crevasse-squeeze ridges and marginal formations), the results of the glacial landform mapping via machine learning, and the collected and newly obtained absolute dates (C-14, Be, OSL etc.) of sediments and landforms related to the deglaciation of the SE sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia with the lines of the ice-margin positions. The data consists of three datasets described separately.

Researchers:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Reconstruction of ice stream dynamics and deglaciation of the SE sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia \(Izp-2024/1-0193\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-04-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Glacial landforms of Latvia

This dataset includes mapped polygons or crestlines of glacial landforms in Latvia from 1-m-resolution LiDAR DEM. The mapping was done manually on-screen by project's personnel in ArcGis Pro and Quantum GIS software. The data is in vector format in the LKS92/Latvia TM (EPSG:3059) projection, and will be compiled in a singular GeoPackage and File Geodatabase (FGDB) files.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data are generated for the reconstruction of the dynamics of the SE sector of the Sandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia. Data are mapped from 1-m-resolution LiDAR DEM.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

geospatial data of glacial landform boundaries or crestlines

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

GeoParquet, GeoPackage, File Geodatabase (FGDB)

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

During this project, a new dataset will be generated that will include glacial landforms mapped from 1-m-resolution LiDAR DEM that has not previously done in Latvia.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

All scientists working in the fields of Quaternary geology, geomorphology and numerical modelling related to the development of glacial landforms, dynamics, subglacial processes, and deglaciation of the Pleistocene Ice Sheets, especially the Scandinavian (Fennoscandian) Ice Sheet.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will describe the mapping source and type of data and the description of the specified glacial landform type.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Will be provided after the acceptance of publication

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Geographic information System software such as ESRI ArcGis Pro, Quantum Gis or similar.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

The generated data will be freely available except for commercial purposes as there may arise a need to generate data in specific resolutions, scales and prepare them in a specified format for specified usage, which would acquire additional work.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

costs covered by project's funding.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kristaps Lamsters (0000-0002-4523-1537)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be prepared during the project and published in Zenodo.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Generated data will be stored at several places: internal hard disks on portable laptops and office computers, external hard disks, cloud storage.

Microsoft OneDrive will be used as cloud storage during the project and fast data sharing as personnel of the University of Latvia has free cloud space up to 1 TB.

External SSD (solid state drives) will be used as well for data storage and sharing during and after the project. Several SSDs will be purchased during the project as planned.

A compilation of External Hard Drives will be also used as data storage and backup server with a space of up to 4 TB.

For geospatial data we will also use an institutional server of the Faculty of Science and Technology with access control.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Modelled glacial landforms of Latvia

Dataset comprises of the modelled results of the glacial landform mapping via machine learning. The data is in vector format (GeoParquet) in the LKS92/Latvia TM (EPSG:3059) projection, and will be compiled in a singular GeoPackage file. The production workflow will be available at the project's GitHub repository (https://github.com/site_to/repo).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data generation is to explore the usage of glacial landforms mapped by employing machine learning techniques for reconstruction of ice stream dynamics and deglaciation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

GeoParquet, GeoPackage

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered, but there is no freely available data of that sort, which would aid in achieving the aim.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers, nature conservation agencies (e.g. for specific biotope mapping), natural resource managers (e.g. for material deposit surveys).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GitHub

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

The relevant code will be accessible in the project's GitHub repository to ensure version control and collaboration opportunities within the project. It will be made public whenever the relevant research paper is published to ensure the publishing of the paper. The data will be accessible in Zenodo.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software with support for the GeoParquet or the GeoPackage standard can be used to access the data.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Both, GeoParquet and GeoPackage standards, are a part of Open Geospatial Consortium.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

Data can be used, shared and adapted as long as attribution is given. There may be commercial purposes for which the author would prepare separate data in a specified format for specified usage.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

As long as the server is up.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kristaps Lamsters (0000-0002-4523-1537)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Generated data will be stored at several places: internal hard disks on portable laptops and office computers, external hard disks, cloud storage.

Microsoft OneDrive will be used as cloud storage during the project and fast data sharing as personnel of the University of Latvia has free cloud space up to 1 TB.

External SSD (solid state drives) will be used as well for data storage and sharing during and after the project. Several SSDs will be purchased during the project as planned.

A compilation of External Hard Drives will be also used as data storage and backup server with a space of up to 4 TB.

For geospatial data we will also use an institutional server of the Faculty of Science and Technology with access control.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Deglaciation chronology and ice margin positions in Latvia

Dataset comprises both previously collected and newly obtained absolute dating results (e.g., radiocarbon [C-14], cosmogenic nuclide [Be], optically stimulated luminescence [OSL] etc.) from sediments and landforms associated with the deglaciation of the southeastern sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet in Latvia and mapped ice margin position lines.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of this dataset is to compile and produce chronological data necessary for reconstructing the timing and pattern of deglaciation in the southeastern sector of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet (SIS) in Latvia. This dataset provides critical temporal control for ice margin positions and the development of glacial landforms.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Machine-readable text
- Other

Chronological data from absolute dating methods including radiocarbon (C-14), cosmogenic nuclide exposure dating (^{10}Be), and optically stimulated luminescence (OSL).

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV

- XLS
- Others

GeoPackage and File Geodatabase, GIS-compatible formats for spatial representation of sample sites and ice margin positions

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science

<http://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.848117>

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset will be useful to researchers in Quaternary science, glacial geology, geomorphology, geochronology, and climate history. It may also support numerical ice-sheet modelling, and regional stratigraphic correlation. Agencies involved in geological mapping, education, and natural resource management may also benefit.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

No. Metadata will include information about the dating method, material dated, location, stratigraphy, and original publication (if reused).

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be made accessible after acceptance of related publications.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Data will be stored in Zenodo or similar open-access repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Spreadsheet software (e.g., Excel), GIS software (e.g., QGIS), R, Python

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0

Free

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-10

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2035-03-08

As long as the repository service (e.g., Zenodo) remains operational.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

All newly obtained dates will follow standard laboratory protocols. Radiocarbon ages will be recalibrated using the latest calibration curve at the time of calibration.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Covered by project funds.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Normunds Stivrins (0000-0002-1136-0146)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Covered during project realization. No additional post-project costs expected

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

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No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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